

FEATURES OF MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM FOR MOISTURE CONTENT IN FEED MATERIALS

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Abstract. This article provides a systematic analysis of the grinding process in obtaining feed products from plants. The application of a pressing system in the grinding process, as well as the automation of equipment and the development of a control system that monitors the operational state of the equipment and determines optimal parameters, are discussed.

A dielectric method for monitoring the moisture content of feed materials is proposed. This method enables the rational control of processes that reduce the moisture content of feed mass using low-energy electrical potentials. The stabilization of the moisture level in plant-based and bulk materials based on dielectric permeability is ensured by a moisture meter. This allows for the processing of controlled materials under external physical influences, as well as monitoring and managing storage in silos, processing, and drying processes and parameters.

The article discusses the mathematical modeling of an automated system for plant grinding, optimizing its parameters to enhance production efficiency. It also presents the functional diagram of an experimental moisture measurement device for feed products and a block diagram of a technological control and monitoring system for feed production.

Keywords: feed, plant-based feed, moisture, dielectric method, grinding, mathematical modeling, moisture meter.

Introduction. Modern moisture measurement methods for solid and bulk plant-based feed materials rely on converting moisture content into other physical quantities using advanced measurement technologies. A significant portion of plant materials' physical, chemical, mechanical, and technological properties depend on moisture content. Drying and moisturizing processes are used in agriculture to measure the moisture content of materials. Therefore, the quantitative determination of moisture is essential in almost all sectors of the economy and in scientific research related to various theoretical justifications and fields of knowledge.

Materials and Methods. To characterize the moisture content in solid and bulk feed products, two values are typically used: *moisture content (U)* and *moisture (W)*, expressed in relative units or as a percentage.

Moisture content refers to the ratio of the mass of moisture (M) (water) in the material to the mass of the absolutely dry material (M_0).

$$= \frac{M}{M_0}. \quad (1)$$

Moisture W is the ratio of the mass of moisture M in the material to the mass of the wet material M_w , i.e.:

$$W = \frac{M}{M_w} = \frac{M}{M_0} + M. \quad (2)$$

As a result, water can penetrate the material structure through the following mechanisms:

- Absorption on the surface and in pores;

- Hydration of polar groups in macromolecules;
- Incorporation into the crystal lattice of mineral components as crystallohydrates.

The mass of the material received by the consumer is referred to as the working mass of the material. If the material is dried at room temperature, the external moisture evaporates, and the sample reaches an air-dry state. When ground to a particle size of up to 0.2 mm, the mass of such a sample is called the analytical mass of the material.

However, in its natural state, a significant amount of moisture is retained by capillary and sorption forces. To remove this moisture, the material is heated to 105°C [1].

A portion of the water evaporated during heating constitutes the total moisture content of the material's working mass. As a result, the dry mass of the material remains. Further heating leads to the breakdown of bonds in crystal hydrates and the release of chemically bound water.

The total moisture index of the working mass of a material is defined as the ratio of the mass of moisture released at the dehydration temperature to the mass of the analyzed sample. This is expressed by the following formula:

$$W_h = \frac{m_a - m_d}{m_a}, \quad (3)$$

where:

- m_d - is the mass of the dry material obtained at the dehydration temperature.

Monitoring and measuring the moisture content of materials in specified units is essential since any deviation from the agreed specifications between the supplier and the consumer can result in severe penalties. Therefore, moisture monitoring devices used in measurement systems must meet the following requirements [2]:

- Rapid response time to prevent the production of low-quality materials;
- Low measurement error and high repeatability to ensure compliance with the specifications of commercial materials.

When studying the high-frequency electromagnetic method, constructing a mathematical model of a high-frequency device is of significant importance. This allows for obtaining a precise mathematical description of the transformation function and the influence functions of the primary affecting quantities.

The selection of the measurement transducer, its operating principles, and its design is crucial when designing moisture control instruments. Studying the relationship between moisture and frequency-moisture characteristics helps determine the transformation functions of a dielectric moisture control device. This involves analyzing how the "moisture-dielectric properties" of materials change within the studied frequency range, selecting the optimal operating frequency, and choosing the appropriate measurement transducer [3].

The complex conductivity $\tilde{\sigma}$ of a non-polar solid dielectric is determined by complex polarization effects [4].

Accordingly, the frequency dependence of dielectric permittivity is influenced by the real and imaginary parts of electronic and ionic polarization. From this, it follows that the real and imaginary parts

$$\tilde{\epsilon} = \epsilon' - \gamma\epsilon'' \quad (4)$$

are functions of the applied field and are determined using $\tilde{\alpha}_1(\omega)$ **and** $\tilde{\alpha}_i(\omega)$. The tangent of the **dielectric loss angle** is expressed by the following formula:

$$\epsilon' = \epsilon; \epsilon'' = \sigma / \omega; \operatorname{tg} \delta = \epsilon'' / \epsilon' = \sigma / \omega \epsilon'; \quad \epsilon^* = \epsilon(1 - j \operatorname{tg} \delta), \quad (5)$$

where: ω is the angular frequency, ε is the dielectric permittivity, ε' and ε'' are the real and imaginary components of the dielectric permittivity, $\text{tg}\delta$ - is the tangent of the dielectric loss angle, σ – is the relative permittivity. By knowing one pair of these parameters, it is possible to calculate any other pair. Additionally, the quality factor of the circuit is given by:

$$Q = 1/\text{tg}\delta$$

where σ' represents the active and σ'' - the reactive components of the complex conductivity.

The practical significance of these results depends on the operating frequency range. The parameters $\tilde{\alpha}_1(\omega)$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_i(\omega)$ correspond to frequencies in the sub-infrared region, maintaining real polarization values. Thus, for the studied materials, the permittivity (ε) remains constant up to microwave frequencies, behaving similarly to a static field condition.

The dielectric method of moisture measurement is based on the difference in the dielectric permittivity of air and water [5].

Their influence is based on the strong dependence of a material's dielectric permittivity on its moisture content. This is due to the ε unusually high dielectric constant of water (20°C да ≈ 81). In the medium frequency range (0.1–30 MHz), measurement is performed by determining the capacitance $C = C_0 \cdot \varepsilon$ of a capacitor, where the test material is placed between its plates (electrodes). The capacitance is expressed as C_0 where: C_0 is the capacitance of the empty capacitor, ε is the relative permittivity of the material. In the ultra-high frequency range (30 MHz and above), measurement is conducted by determining the resonant frequency of a cavity resonator containing the moist material [6].

Since the relative permittivity of water is a constant value close to 81, while most dry materials have permittivities between 2 and 10 (for example, sand has a permittivity of about 3 to 4), there is a significant difference between the dielectric permittivity of water and that of dry materials.

This difference can be measured and compared with a specific moisture value.

In this case, the moisture value of the test material is usually output as a standard signal (e.g., 0–10V or 0–20mA) based on its specific weight moisture content.

In other words, the more water or moisture a material contains, the closer its dielectric permittivity ε_p 81. Even a slight change in the material's moisture content leads to a significant variation in its dielectric properties, including changes in both dielectric permittivity and the tangent of the dielectric loss angle $\text{tg}\delta$.

The increase in the dielectric constant as a function of moisture content can typically be described by the following relationship:

$$\Delta_\varepsilon = \varepsilon_v f(\xi, n, i, r, k \dots), \quad (6)$$

Here, ε_v is the permittivity of free water; ξ is a factor determined by the distribution and form of moisture addition; n is the ratio of free to bound moisture volumes; r is also the ratio of free to bound moisture volumes; i is the conductivity ratio of bound and free water; k is the conductivity ratio of dry material to moisture. When analyzing scientific studies on grinding and pressing plant-based products [1-3], a mathematical description of the operation of a single-screw press for food extraction is proposed. According to this model, the average velocity of movement in the screw channel is determined as follows:

$$\bar{V} = \int_0^{X^*} V_1(X) dX + \int_{X^*}^1 V_0(1 - X^*) - \frac{n}{1 + 2n} +$$

(7)

$$+ \left(\frac{dP}{dZ} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} X^{*\frac{1+2n}{n}} + \frac{n}{1+n} \left(\frac{dP}{dZ} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} (1-X^*)^{\frac{1+n}{n}} \left[\frac{1+3n}{1+3n} (1-X^*) - 1 \right]$$

Additionally, a mathematical modeling description of the protein-lipid fraction pressing process for food materials is also provided.

The corresponding equation is as follows:

$$\frac{\delta g}{\delta \tau} - \frac{1}{Re} \left[m \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y^2} + \frac{1}{y} \frac{\delta g}{\delta y} \right] \left(\frac{\delta g}{\delta y} \right)^{m-1} = -Eu \cdot \sin(\beta \tau), 0 \leq \tau \leq 1, \quad (8)$$

The boundary conditions are defined as follows:

$$g(r, 0) = 0, \frac{\partial g(0, \tau)}{\partial r} = 0, \quad g(1, r) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Yu.P. Matsuk proposed the following **mathematical model formula** for the **productivity of screw presses**, QQQ, in tons per day [4]:

$$Q_{KEH} = K_H \cdot H_B \frac{10000}{K(100 - W_K)} \cdot \left(\mu \frac{100 + W_{qa.m.} - M_{qa.m.}}{100} \right), \quad (10)$$

Here: Q_{KEH} is the useful work efficiency coefficient of the pressing technology. J is the percentage of bran output from wheat.

Here: W_K , W_M , $W_{qa.m.}$ – the moisture percentage of the output feed, pulp, and returned products, respectively. M_K , M_M , $M_{qa.m.}$ – the oil content percentage of the output bran, pulp, and returned products, respectively. It is assumed that the movement of oil through the porous structure of the raw material occurs in a laminar flow regime and follows Darcy's Law. According to this law, in the absence of mass forces, the velocity of the liquid phase in a porous medium is expressed using the following mathematical model:

$$V_F(z) = -\frac{k}{\mu} gradP(z), \quad (11)$$

Here: μ – the dynamic viscosity of the medium, k – the permeability of the porous medium.

As a result of the above mathematical modeling, modern automation technologies in production can significantly accelerate and simplify the grain grinding process. For this, it is necessary to use special automation systems based on mathematical models.

In our research on measuring the moisture content of plant-based feed products, experiments are planned using cylindrical capacitive and electrode-based dielectric moisture meters as primary measuring transducers. In these primary transducers, the measured feed product is placed in their electric field, allowing the determination of moisture content [7].

Typically, digital moisture meters consist of a sensor, a measuring oscillator, a reference oscillator, a temperature correction device, and counters sequentially connected to the measuring and reference oscillators.

The dielectric grain moisture meter includes a capacitive primary transducer, a high-frequency measuring oscillator equipped with an automatic active resistance stabilization system for its oscillation circuit, a high-frequency reference oscillator, a control signal distributor, a microcomputer controlled by synchronous pulses of a clock generator, and a frequency divider.

Additionally, it consists of a two-position electronic switch and operational amplifiers with resistors in parallel negative feedback.

Below, in Figure 1, the functional diagram of an experimental device illustrating the features of a feed material moisture control and management system is presented.

Figure 1. Functional Diagram of a Dielectric Capacitive Moisture Meter for Feed Products

Here 1 - Primary measuring transducer, 2,3 - Measuring oscillators, 4 - Signal shaping block, 5 - Reference oscillator, 6 - Signal shaping block, 7 - Clock generator, 8 - Frequency divider, 9 - Signal distribution block, 10 - Arithmetic counter, 11 - Digital-to-analog converter, 12 - Control signal distributor, 13 - Analog-to-digital converter, 14 - Digital display, 15 - Power supply unit.

Analyzing the operation of this moisture meter is essential to ensure its proper functionality in achieving the intended measurement objectives. Various researchers have proposed different measurement methods, all aimed at utilizing the dielectric method for measuring moisture content.

At the State Scientific Laboratory of the Uzbek National Metrology Institute, studies are being conducted on monitoring the moisture content of feed products using a rapid discrete dielectric method.

The main goal of these studies is to develop modern primary measuring transducers for monitoring the moisture content of existing food products, including grains, grain-processing products, plant-based feeds, and their by-products such as flour and groats.

These transducers are not only measurement instruments but also form the lower tier of a computer-controlled system, where primary measurement signals are obtained, processed in a controller device, and displayed on a computer screen.

By implementing industrial controllers, an automated control system can solve various production tasks, such as increasing the speed of technological processes, automatically removing faulty equipment from operation, and dynamically adjusting process routes.

Studies have shown that the most technically advanced approach for measuring the moisture content of plant-based feed is through a dielectric moisture meter [8]. This modern dielectric moisture meter consists of the following components: A capacitive primary transducer, connected to the input of a high-frequency measuring oscillator, A high-frequency reference oscillator, A data recording unit, First and second signal shaping blocks, An arithmetic conversion block, A signal distribution block, A frequency divider and clock generator. This advanced measuring system allows for precise moisture control in feed products, ensuring efficiency in agricultural and food-processing industries.

Purpose of Using the Measuring Instrument. The primary goal of using this measuring instrument is to enhance measurement accuracy by eliminating technical errors and improving the overall reliability of the device. Additionally, it aims to integrate both laboratory (single-point) and continuous moisture measurements for the monitored material.

Based on the results obtained during the study of the existing problem [9-10], it was concluded that automating the production and processing of feed products requires the development of an automated technological process control system.

The key components of this system include: A programmable logic controller (PLC) – to manage the control system, A primary signal monitoring transducer – to measure and regulate input data, An operator station (industrial computer) – to oversee and control processes, Local control panels – for manual adjustments and monitoring. This system provides efficient and accurate moisture monitoring in feed products, contributing to process automation and improved production quality in the agriculture and food-processing industries.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the Technological Control and Management System in Feed Production

The **control system** consists of **three hierarchical levels**: This includes **sensors** for measuring various **parameters**, as well as **actuating mechanisms**: **Sensors**: Moisture, temperature, and pressure sensors, **Actuating mechanisms**: Frequency converters, measuring pumps, pneumatically and hydraulically controlled valves, mixers. This level handles the

automatic collection and processing of measured parameters, equipment control, and direct digital control (DDC) according to technological regulations. It includes: **Microprocessor devices (controllers)** – responsible for adjusting parameters based on pre-programmed settings. This level focuses on: **Data processing, logging, and archiving, Displaying information, System interaction interfaces, Controlling pumps and other critical equipment.**

The main **communication network** between the **server, controllers, and operator stations** is a **10 Mbps ETHERNET-based Local Area Network (LAN)**. Controllers send: **Periodic measurement data** to operator stations at set intervals; **Event data** related to analog signal adjustments and system errors.

Automating **feed silos and other plant-based food processing and storage facilities** has become a **crucial challenge**. This is especially relevant for **drying, storing, and transporting feed materials**.

Implementing **automated process control systems** offers: **Real-time monitoring and adjustment** of technological parameters; **More efficient data collection, control, and management; Optimization of drying, storage, and transport processes; Increased economic efficiency and competitiveness** of production facilities. By integrating a **multi-level human-machine control system**, modern feed production and storage operations can achieve **higher accuracy, efficiency, and reliability**.

Conclusions. Feed planning and collection should be conducted based on the mass of dry matter units. The paper provides a detailed analysis of rapid moisture measurement methods for feed materials, along with a functional diagram of the developed moisture measuring device. A mathematical model has been proposed to describe the grinding and pressing process of plant-based materials in a single-screw press, aimed at feed production. The dielectric method for monitoring feed moisture levels has been suggested, which allows for accurate control of moisture content in feed mass. To stabilize the moisture level of plant products and bulk materials through their dielectric permittivity, it is necessary to consider external environmental factors affecting the measured materials. Enhancing measurement accuracy and minimizing instrumental errors within the measuring range requires: Careful calibration of measurement instruments; Implementation of automated control systems; Adjusting for external factors influencing measurement results by optimizing feed moisture measurement and control processes, the efficiency and reliability of feed production and storage can be significantly improved.

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